

INFANTILE PYLORIC STENOSIS

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Abstract:

Food and other stomach contents pass through the pylorus, the lower part of the stomach, to enter the small intestine. Pyloric stenosis is a narrowing of the pylorus. When a baby has pyloric stenosis, this narrowing of the pyloric channel prevents food from emptying out from the stomach.

Key Words: Pylorus, Stenosis, Narrowing & Stomach

Pyloric stenosis is a narrowing of the pylorus, the opening from the stomach into the small intestine. It's thought that babies who develop pyloric stenosis are not born with it, but have progressive thickening of the pylorus after birth. A baby will start to show symptoms when the pylorus is so thick that the stomach can't empty properly.

Incidence:

It's more likely to affect firstborn male infants and also runs in. Most infants who have it develop symptoms 3 to 5 weeks after birth.

Etiology:

- ✓ The cause of this thickening isn't clear. It might be a combination of several things; for example, use of erythromycin (an antibiotic) in babies in the first 2 weeks of life
- ✓ Antibiotics given to moms at the end of pregnancy or during breastfeeding.

Clinical Manifestations:

- ✓ Vomiting.
- ✓ Changes in stools. Babies with pyloric stenosis usually have fewer, smaller stools because little or no food is reaching the intestines.
- ✓ Failure to gain weight
- ✓ Dehydrated.
- ✓ Wave of peristalsis

Diagnosis:

- ✓ Complete history taking
- ✓ Physical examination-
 - Failure to maintain growth since birth will be noted.
 - Lump in the abdomen, which usually is firm and movable and feels like an olive. it's a strong indication that a baby has pyloric stenosis.
- ✓ Abdominal ultrasound- The enlarged, thickened pylorus can be seen on ultrasound images
- ✓ Barium swallow - view the pyloric area of the stomach to see if there is any narrowing or blockage
- ✓ X-rays - view the pyloric area of the stomach to see if there is any narrowing or blockage.
- ✓ Electrolytes test - An electrolyte imbalance often happens due to the ongoing vomiting of stomach acid and dehydration.

Treatment:

- ✓ Dehydration or electrolyte problems in the blood will be corrected with intravenous (IV) fluids, usually within 24 hours.
- ✓ Surgical Procedure- Pyloromyotomy, which involves cutting through the thickened muscles of the pylorus, will relieve the blockage.

Conclusion:

Pyloric stenosis is a narrowing of the opening from the stomach to the first part of the small intestine . Symptoms include projectile vomiting this most often occurs after the baby is fed. .The cause of pyloric stenosis is unclear. Treatment initially begins by correcting dehydration and electrolyte problems. This is then typically followed by surgery

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